

AZO AND MERCURATED AZO DERIVATIVES OF SOME 2-AMINOTHIAZOLES

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Several 2-aminothiazoles have been converted into azo and mercurated azo dyes which have been subjected to antibacterial and antifungal tests.

The antibacterial (Yoshio, *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1951, 71, 709) as well as chemotherapeutic activities (Schaeffer and Toomey, *Amer. J. Med.*, 1949, 67, 6; Bambas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 671), such as antithyroid (Bovet *et al.*, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1951, 37, Oct. 7), hypotensive and antihistaminic (Kaye and Parris, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1751) activities of thiazole derivatives suggested an investigation of some of the new derivatives of 4-substituted 2-aminothiazoles. The recent report of a few azo dyes showing urogenital analgesic (Steinberg, U.S.P. 2, 580, 250/1951) and antiviral properties (Takeo *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1951, 71, 972; Minoru Hiyama, *ibid.*, 1952, 72, 1374) has led the author to prepare some azo derivatives of thiazoles and to test their chemotherapeutic properties. As the introduction of mercury into the azo compounds considerably enhances their antibacterial properties, as has already been reported (Guha Sarkar and Rout, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 364) and in view of Proskowriakoff and Raiziss's observation (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 1974) to the same effect, it has been considered further to mercurate these azo dyes and test their antibacterial and other possible medicinal properties.

Seventeen 4-aryl-substituted 2-aminothiazoles have been synthesised by the method of King and Hlavacek, as reported earlier (Mahapatra, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 527). These aminothiazoles were coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide in a sodium acetate buffer, when coloured azo dyes were obtained.

It has been assumed that the azo group attaches itself to the thiazole nucleus at C₅, and this assumption is based on the evidences of Bogert and Chertcoff (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1924, 10, 418; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2864) who have observed that when diazotised *p*-nitroaniline and sulphanilic acid are coupled with 2-aminothiazole, the azo group is attached to C₅ of the thiazole nucleus. Ganapati and Venkataraman (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 348) and Beyer and Wolter (*Chem. Ber.*, 1952, 85, 1077) have made similar observations.

This conclusion is further supported by the fact that when C₄ and C₅ of the thiazole nucleus are attached to aryl or alkyl groups, azo-dye formation does not take place.

This indirectly proves that the coupling takes place at C₂ when C₄ is already occupied. The possibility of the azo group being fixed to the phenyl nucleus at C₄ carrying OH or NH₂ group is also excluded due to the inability of such compounds to couple with phenyldiazonium acetate, when the 5th positions of the above thiazole nuclei are already occupied.

Mercurated azo dyes have been prepared by mercurating first sulphanilamide with mercuric acetate, when one acetoxymercuri group enters the position *ortho* to the NH₂ group of the sulphanilamide molecule. This mercurated sulphanilamide was subsequently diazotised and coupled with 2-aminothiazoles to afford mercurated azo dyes.

The preparation of different azo- and mercurated azothiazoles has been illustrated by reporting one example in each case. The analytical and bactericidal data are recorded in Tables I, II and III.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-(2:5-Dimethyl)-phenyl-2-amino-5-azophenyl-(p)-sulphonamidothiazole.—Sulphanilamide (1 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) and water (100 c.c.), was diazotised by treatment with a solution of NaNO₂ (0.5 g.) in 30 c.c. of water in an ice-bath. The resulting diazo solution, buffered with sodium acetate (10 g.); was added gradually with stirring to a previously well-cooled solution of 4-(2:5-dimethyl)-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (1 g. dissolved in 2 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and the whole diluted to 80 c.c. with water). After addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for another hour when a dark chocolate coloured dye separated, which was filtered and washed thoroughly. The dye was finally recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 122°, yield 85%. (Found: C, 51.87; H, 3.91; N, 18.35; S, 16.79. C₁₇H₁₇O₂N₂S₂ requires C, 52.71; H, 4.39; N, 18.09; S, 16.54%).

TABLE I

Aryl-2-amino-5-azophenyl-(p)-sulphonamidothiazoles.

No.	C ₁ aryl group.	M.P.	Yield.	Colour of the azo compound.	% Nitrogen.		Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	Ph	215°	72%	Chocolate-red	19.17	19.49	18.02	17.82
2	<i>p</i> -Me.C ₆ H ₄ .	181°	82	Do	18.9	18.76	17.83	17.16
3	<i>p</i> -Et.C ₆ H ₄ .	207°	85	Red	17.52	18.09	15.87	16.54
4	(3:4) Me ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	217°	75	Chocolate-red	17.81	18.09	16.10	16.54
5	(2:5) Me ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .	122°	85	Dark chocolate	18.35	18.09	16.79	16.54
6	<i>p</i> -MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .	183°	68	Chocolate-brown	17.81	17.99	16.83	16.45
7	<i>p</i> -EtO.C ₆ H ₄ .	184°	77	Reddish brown	16.91	17.37	14.93	15.88
8	<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .	203°	65	Do	18.97	18.66	17.83	17.07
9	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .	115°	68	Deep chocolate	18.13	18.66	16.35	17.07
10	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .	194°	71	Orange-red	18.30	17.79	16.09	16.26
11	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ .	150°	74	Chocolate-red	15.73°	15.98	14.02	14.61
12	<i>m</i> -NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .	235° (d)	75	Do	21.93	22.45	17.53	17.11
13	α -C ₁₀ H ₇ .	103°	79	Chocolate	16.87	17.11	14.79	15.64
14	β -C ₁₀ H ₇ .	197°	83	Red	16.85	17.11	15.78	15.64
15	2-C ₄ H ₉ S(2-thienyl).	277°	73	Chocolate-red	18.62	19.18	25.85	26.30
16	C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .	178°	81	Orange-yellow	18.38	18.09	15.88	16.54
17	(<i>p</i>)MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .	185°	87	Dirty red	15.93	16.78	15.10	15.35

m-Acetoxymercurisulphanilamide.—Sulphanilamide (17 g.) was dissolved in dilute acetic acid and treated with an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (40 g. in 400 c.c. of water), acidified with acetic acid. There was an immediate precipitation and the reaction mixture was well stirred and kept overnight. The precipitate was collected and washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with alcohol and very dilute acetic acid, m.p. >350°, yield 85%. (Found: Hg, 45.85. C₈H₁₀O₄N₂SHg requires Hg, 46.51%).

4-(2:5-Dimethyl)-phenyl-2-amino-5-azo-(*o*-acetoxymercuri)-phenyl-(*p*)-sulphonamidothiazole.—*m*-Acetoxymercuri-sulphanilamide (2 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (8 c.c.) and diluted with water up to 200 c.c. It was diazotised and the resulting solution, buffered with sodium acetate (15 g.), was added gradually with stirring to a previously well-cooled solution of 4-(2:5-dimethyl)-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (1 g. dissolved in 2 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and the whole diluted to 100 c.c. with water). After addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for another hour. The brownish red dye separating was collected and washed thoroughly, m.p. 117°, yield 50%. (Found: Hg, 30.55. C₁₉H₁₉O₄N₂S₂Hg requires Hg, 31.0%)=

TABLE II
4-Aryl-2-amino-5-azo-(o-acetoxymercuro)-phenyl-(p)-sulphonamidothiazoles.

* No. of compound.	M.P.	Yield.	Colour of the mercurated azo dye.	% Mercury.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	133°	72%	Chocolate-red	31.73	32.41
2	172°	78	Chocolate	30.96	31.69
3	139°	68	Red	31.31	31.00
4	171°	75	Brownish red	30.55	31.00
5	117°	80	Do	30.61	31.00
6	191°	91	Do	30.39	30.91
7	194°	79	Red	30.45	30.26
8	Decomp. & softens but does not melt.	83	Deep chocolate	30.89	31.59
9	178°	87	Do	31.21	31.59
10	148°	89	Brown	30.81	30.69
11	195°	73	Reddish brown	28.13	28.74
12	Does not melt at 350°; only softens.	72	Brownish red	31.73	31.64
13	118°	85	Do	30.05	29.98
14	141°	87	Do	28.93	29.98
15	Softens & decomp. but does not melt even at 350°.	71	Chocolate-red	32.34	32.10
16	236°	83	Deep chocolate	31.20	31.00
17	173°	87	Brown	29.79	29.63

* Nature of the C₄-aryl group corresponds to those in Table I.

Antibacterial test.—The Rideal-Walker drop dilution method was used for the comparative antibacterial study. The results of biological tests indicating the maximum effective dilution (M.E.D.) of the antibacterials at 10 minutes' contact are shown against the compounds in Table III. The temperature was 37° and the test organisms were 24 hours cultures of *E. coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

TABLE III
Antibacterial activity.

No. of comp. (vide Table I)	M.E.D.		No. of comp. (vide Table II)	M.E.D.	
	<i>E. Coll.</i>	<i>Staph. a.</i>		<i>E. Coll.</i>	<i>Staph. a.</i>
1	1:1,000	1:6000	1	1:2000	1:10000
2	"	"	2	1:1000	"
3	"	1:8000	3	"	"
4	"	"	4	"	"
5	"	"	5	"	"
6	"	"	6	"	"
7	"	"	7	"	"
8	"	1:10000	8	"	"
9	"	"	9	1:12000	"
10	"	"	10	"	1:15000
11	"	"	11	"	"
12	"	"	12	1:5000	"
13	"	"	13	1:2000	"
14	"	"	14	"	"
15	"	1:6000	15	"	1:10000
16	"	"	16	"	"
17	"	"	17	"	"

It is observed from the data, that 2-aminothiazoles are quite active against *Staphylococcus aureus* at a maximum dilution of 1:8000, while the compounds are not appreciably active against *E. coli*. The azo derivatives are similarly active against *Staph. aureus* and *E. coli* more or less in the same range of dilution. The mercurated azo derivatives are more active, being active against *Staph. aureus* at a dilution of 1:15,000. Thus introduction of phenylazosulphonamido group does not enhance the antibacterial activity, though the acetoxymercuri group enhances the antibacterial activities nearly two times. The antibacterial data are recorded in Table III.

Fungicidal tests.—For fungicidal assay, the spore germination method of Montgomery and Moore (*J. Pomol. & Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 18, 253) with a slight modification was used. *Piricularia orizae*, Cav. was used as the test fungus. The mercurated azo dyes showed the maximum fungitoxic activity. Most of the mercurated azo dyes in Table III inhibited the spore germination of the fungus at a concentration of 8-9 p.p.m., while the unmercurated ones showed little fungitoxic activity. The details of the fungicidal work will be published elsewhere.

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